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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Facial Scrub

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ABSTRACT

Cosmetics are defined as the products used for the purpose of beautifying, cleansing, promoting attractiveness or alternating the appearance. The aim of study is to formulate and evaluate a face scrub with incorporation of the sapodilla as an active ingredient. For the purpose of enhancing skin beauty, several skin conditions are developed, such as skin protection, sunscreen, anti-acne, and anti-wrinkle products. Despite the enormous health benefits of synthetic substances, which once more cause environmental destruction, demand for herbal items and cosmetics is rising daily. Due to their dual functionality as medications and cosmetics, herbal cosmetics are in high demand nowadays. The name itself indicates that herbal cosmetics are natural and they do not contain any chemicals. Natural ingredients have no side effects, making them the safest and greatest products to use on a daily basis. A facial scrub is a cosmetic or a beauty product used to exfoliate and clean the skin on the face and body. Blackheads, whiteheads, sebum, and skin cells can all be removed by using face scrubs. In this face scrub, sapodilla is used as an active ingredient. The other ingredients like carbopol, methyl paraben, triethanolamine, propylene glycol, sodium lauryl sulphate were added into this face scrub gel. The prepared face scrub were evaluated for various parameters such as organoleptic properties, pH, irritability, washability, grittiness, extrudability, foamability, spreadability and found to be satisfactory outcome. The prepared formulation works well as a scrub that encourages healthy and radiant skin.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics areas article meant to be poured, rubbed, sprinkled, sprayed, or injected into the human body for cleansing, beautifying, boosting

attractiveness, or altering appearance without harming structure of function under the terms of the food drug and cosmetic act. The body's largest organ is the skin. It act as the body's defence mechanism. Skins acts as a wrapper- like barrier

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for protection. Maintaining everything below. Skin is a sensory organ that shows a person's health. Cosmetics are described as the products that are used to cleanse, beautify, promote beauty, or alternate one's appearance. Different herbs have been utilized for cleaning beautifying, and managing them since ancient times. The skin of the face is the largest part of the body and reflects an individual's health. Cosmeceuticals are a marketer's dream, allowing for the incorporation of an infinite number of active ingredients obtained from a wide range of natural and synthetic sources into skin care products. Vitamins, antioxidants, minerals, herbs, hormones, anti-inflammatories, anti-depressants mood-altering aromas (aromatherapy), and even exotic ingredients like placenta and amniotic fluid have all been utilized in cosmeceuticals. Natural beauty blessings and cosmetics aid in the presentation and enhancement of a person's beauty and personality. People's beauty and personality. People nowadays prefer natural foods, herbal treatments, and natural healing procedures for a healthy lifestyle. Herbal cosmetics are formulations with phytochemicals from various plant sources that regulate skin function and give essential nutrients for healthy skin. Herbal cosmetics are natural plants and their products that are utilized in cosmetic preparations for their aromatic value. Because there is a widespread assumption that chemical-based cosmetics are harmful, herbal goods have sparked a desire for natural products and natural extracts in cosmetic formulations. By eliminating peripheral dead cells and support to the development of cells in the sub-epidermal layer. Herbal exfoliating scrub reduces age-related problems and nullifies the environment's destruction. Scrub can be used to clean the surface technically with the use of herbal products containing Antioxidant, Vitamins, Antiseptics, Anti-aging. Antibacterial characteristics that contribute help depth to clean the skin and make it shiny and glowing and

Exfoliating dead skin cells, using facial scrub is simple first, choose a regular scrub that is suitable for your skin type then apply the scrub into moisturized skin and gently rub it in for one minute, finally rinse it off with water. The use of scrub is suitable for all skin types, but the choice of essential oil used as an ingredient in the scrub should vary depending on the individual's skin type. There are three types of skin i.e. oily, dry, sensitive skin. Yes, a gentle massage with a scrub gel can help stimulate blood circulation and oxygenation of the skin and production of new skin cells. By removing dead skin cells, it can help smooth out rough or uneven patches and reveal brighter, more radiant, looking skin. Facial scrub is a cosmetic or a beauty product or a treatment which cleanses and exfoliates the skin of the face or body. Facial scrubs are beneficial to remove dirt, skin cells and sebum or oil, blackheads and Whiteheads. It helps to maintain skin appearance. There are three kinds of skin types, oily skin, sensitive skin and dry skin. For a person with dry skin must use the facial scrub, which contains the moisturizing and hydrating ingredients. If the person is having sensitive skin, he or she should use gentle scrub. And the person with oily skin should be using an exfoliation which prevents pimples dullness and breakouts and helps to control oiliness. Depending on the skin types facial scrubs are advised to use twice or thrice a week. But for the newbies, facial scrubs are recommended to use weekly. People with dry or sensitive skin types should only exfoliate one or two times a week. In some conditions, people with acne-prone skin are recommended to use products containing salicylic acid and dermatologist-grade 4% glycolic and polyhydroxy acid complex. This helps to exfoliate skin and clear acne with giving smoother appearance.

1. Mango Leaves:

- **Synonym:** Mangifera Indica
- **Family:** Anacardiaceae
- **Biological Source:** The biological source of mango leaves is the plant of Mangifera indica.
- **Description:**
Colour - Dark green
- **Condition:**
Taste - Slightly bitter
- **Chemical Constituent:**
Mango leaves contain a variety of chemical constituents including polyphenols, flavonoids, triterpenoids and essential oils.
- **Uses :**
Boosting immunity, aiding digestion and promoting healthy skin, supporting skin health, etc.
- **Family -** Zingiberaceae.
- **Biological source -** It consists of dried rhizomes of Curcuma longa
- **Description –**
Colour – Yellow to golden orange
- **Condition**
Taste – Bitter and woody
- **Chemical constituents –**
Curcuma longa mainly consist of curcuminoids like curcumin, demethoxy curcumin, and bisdemethoxy curcumin along with essential oil containing compounds like turmerone and zingiberene.
- **Uses**
 - Reduce acne,
 - Glowing skin,
 - Lightens skin,
 - anti- inflammatory,
 - antiseptic,
 - anti- allergic.

2. Neem Leaves:

- **Synonym –** Neem
- **Scientific Name :** Azadirachta Indica
- **Family :** Meliaceae.
- **Biological source :** It consists of dried leaves of Azadirachta indica
- **Description:**
Colour – Vibrant green
Taste - Extremely bitter
- **Chemical constituents :**
Azadirachta indica consist of limonoids, azadirachtin, flavonoids, polyphenols, Nimbinin, Nimbidin, Quercetin, alkaloids and saponins.
- **Uses :**
It has antifungal , antibacterial properties and rich in vitamin which is bone people, with sensitive and oily skin. It help it treating other skin issues and like black heads, pigmentation dullness aging acne, skin problem.

3. Turmeric :

- **Synonym-** Curcuma longa

4. Gram:

- **Synonym:** Chickpea
- **Scientific Name :** Cicer Arietinum
- **Family :** Fabaceae (Leguminosae)
- **Biological Source :** It is obtained from chickpeas which are a type of legume.
- **Description:**
Colour – Light Yellow
- **Condition**
Taste – Mildly nutty and earthy taste
- **Chemical Constituent :**
It is primarily composed of carbohydrates (Starch) ,protein and fiber.
- **Uses :**
Good source of protein and fiber and essential minerals, weight management, skin lightening and even tone, soothing and healing, maintains skins Ph balance.

5. Green Gram

- **Synonym** – Moong Beans
- **Scientific Name** : Vigna Radiata
- **Family** : Fabaceae
- **Biological Source** : The plant Vigna radiata (L.) R. Wilczek also known as green gram.
- **Description**:
Colour – Typically Green
- **Condition**
Taste – Mild slightly sweet
- **Chemical Constituent** :
Vigna Radiata consist of protein, carbohydrates, various minerals, phenolic acids, flavonoids, and tannins.
- **Uses** :
Aiding digestion, supporting weight management, and providing essential nutrients, brighten and even out skin tone, moisturize and hydrate the skin and also have anti-inflammatory and anti-bacterial properties.

6. Rose Water :

- **Synonym** : Attar of roses
- **Scientific Name** : Rosa damascena flower water.
- **Family** : Rosaceae
- **Biological Source** : Rose water is primarily obtained from the petals of the Rosa damascena species, a type of rose known as the Damask rose.
- **Description** :
Colour – Colourless and Clear
Taste – Slightly sweeter
- **Chemical Constituent** :
Rose water consist of 2-phenylethanol (or phenyl ethyl alcohol), citronellol and geraniol.
- **Uses** :
Skincare , haircare, culinary applications , aromatherapy and for general health benefits like easing digestion.

Anatomy of Skin :

The Integumentary system Is Largest Organ And Composed Of Skin, hairs, nails and glands. Epidermis regenerates with New cells every 28 days. This layer measures the thickness of 0.05 to 0.1mm. Epidermis The skin is primarily made up of three layers. The upper layer is the epidermis, the layer below the epidermis is the dermis, and the third and deepest layer is the subcutaneous tissue (see Images. The Common Integument, Section of Skin and The Common Integument, Section of Epidermis.) The epidermis, the outermost layer of skin, provides a waterproof barrier and contributes to skin tone. The dermis, found beneath the epidermis, contains connective tissue, hair follicles, blood vessels, lymphatic vessels, and sweat glands. The deeper subcutaneous tissue (hypodermis) is made of fat and connective tissue. The epidermis is further divided into five layers on thick skin like the palms and soles (stratum basale, stratum spinosum, stratum granulose, stratum lucidum, and stratum corneum, while in other places, the epidermis only has four layers, lacking the stratum lucidum).Dermis is divided into two layers, the papillary dermis (the upper layer) and the reticular dermis (the lower layer). The functions of the skin include: Protection against microorganisms, dehydration, ultraviolet light, and **Mechanical damage**; the skin is the first physical barrier that the human body has against the external environment.

Subcutaneous tissue:

Subcutaneous tissue is the deepest layer of your skin. It's made up mostly of fat cells and connective tissue. The majority of your body fat is stored here. The subcutaneous layer acts as a layer of insulation to protect your internal organs and muscles from shock and changes in temperature. A Cosmetic Product Called a facial Scrub Is used

to hydrate, exfoliate, and clean the Skin on The face. The three types of Skin are Sensitive, oily, and dry skin. Those have dry Skin should wash

their faces with A moisturizer-containing cleanser and then apply moisturizer.

Fig : Anatomy of Skin

Gently scrubbing sensitive skin is recommended To Avoid Clogged pores and To Keep the Skin's oil production in Control, oily Skin needs a scrub that exfoliates deeply. There is no specific Procedure in the procedure in The preparation of rice scrub compared to Other Products, it is a pure natural handcrafted facial scrub, so there is no specific technique. So all We have to do now is Combine the various components in a precise and discrete manner until We get a perfect mixture, which we many Cell a Scrub. There are various forms of scrub that We Might refers to as alternatives. When dead skin cell accumulate on the surface of your skin, your complexion might become bland. That's where exfoliation, specifically the use of a face scrub, might help.

Functions of the skin:

- Provides a protective barrier against mechanical, thermal and physical injury and hazardous substances.
- Prevents loss of moisture.
- Reduces harmful effects of UV radiation.
- Acts as a sensory organ (touch, detects temperature).

- Helps regulate temperature.
- An immune organ to detect infections etc
- Production of vitamin D.

Skin care Preparation

It helps your skin stay in good condition: You're shedding skin cells throughout the day, so it's important to keep your skin glowing and in good condition. An effective routine can help prevent acne, treat wrinkles, and help keep your skin looking its best.

Types of skin care-

- a. Face scrub
- b. Face Pack
- c. Toner
- d. Moisturizer

Definition of face scrub:

"A face scrub is a skincare product used to exfoliate your skin. It helps in the removal of dead skin cells from the surface of your skin, reducing the chances for clogged pores and acne breakouts."

Types of face scrub exits in market:

1. Inorganic face scrub
2. Herbal face scrub

Inorganic face scrub: Facial scrubs contain coarse particles which help to exfoliate the skin containing mainly of inorganic ingredient these face scrub has number of side effect due to chemical present in it

Herbal face scrub: Herbal face scrub maintain the health of skin containing mostly plant product and it has no side effect present in it.

Application of herbal face scrub:

1. Facial scrubs contain coarse particles which help to exfoliate the skin. When you apply a face scrub, the particles rub against your skin and remove all the dirt from your skin pores.
2. It also removes dead skin cells, making your skin smoother and softer.
3. Facial scrubs contain coarse particles which help to exfoliate the skin.

Types of face scrub on its use

1. Acne control scrub
2. Gentle smoothing scrub
3. Microdermabrasion scrub
4. Clarifying scrub

Microdermabrasion scrubs: These scrubs contain fine, abrasive particles that remove the top layer of dead skin to reveal smoother, brighter skin.

Clarifying scrubs: These scrubs contain ingredients such as charcoal or clay that absorb impurities and help clear congested skin.

Preparation of face scrub:

Preparation of face scrub can be carried out by two methods

- A. Fusion Method
- B. Trituration Method

A. Fusion Method: Fusion method is employed when the base is semi solid all the ingredient are fused in a motor pestle

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY:

1. To main objective of present study was to prepare a herbal facial scrub.
2. Collection and authentication of Cucumis melo, Citrullus lanatus, citrus sinensis
3. Different evaluation test are carried out for the prepared herbal Facial formulation
4. It helps in the elimination of acne, pimple, scares, and marks,
5. The prepared formulation of herbal facial scrub was effective for healthy clear and glowing skin.

MATERIALS AND INSTRUMENTS

Material used: materials used for research work were as follows.

List of chemicals

Sr. No	Name	Company Name
1.	Mangifera Indica
2.	Azadirachta Indica
3.	Curcuma Longa
4.	Cicer Arietinum
5.	Vigna Radiata
6.	Rose Water	SDFCT,Mumbai
7.	Sodium Lauryl Sulphate	LABLINE ,Mumbai
8.	Methyl Paraben	LABLIN,Mumbai
9.	Glycerine	SDFCT, Mumbai

Instrument used:

Instrument used for research work as follows.

Sr.No	Name	Model	Manufacturer
1	Digital ph meter	MK VI	LABLINE MUMBAI
2	Digital Balance	AA 2000	LABLINE MUMBAI

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection, Identification and Preparation of Materials

Mangifera Indica , Azadirachta Indica , Curcuma Longa , Cicer Arietinum , Vigna Radiata were collected in plastic bag from DJPS college campus pohetakali,tqpathri. District Parbhani, state Maharashtra, India during the month of may and then it was processed and mounted on herbarium sheet as per procedure of botanical survey of India for identification and Authenticated by Professor Dr. KS.Kadam,asst Professor in Botany, department of Botany.K.K.M.Science college Manwath, District Parbhani, Maharashtra, India. After identification the collected peel were washed gently with tap water followed by distilled water to remove the adhering dust and soil particles, and dried in shaded place at room temperature for 10 days in order to prevent the decomposition of active compounds. After drying, the leaves were chopped into small pieces and grinded into fine powdery form using mechanical grinder.

Preparation of extract

Leaves of Mangifera indica were collected, shade dried at room temperature and ground in a manual mill and sieved with 2 mm copper sieve to form uniform powder. 50 g of dried powdered drug was weighed and filled in the thimble of Soxhlet apparatus. After that the thimble was fixed with the round bottom flask, and the assembly was attached to the condenser. And the paraffin wax

was put at the joints of the assembly for the easy removal of the assembly at the completion of the extraction procedure. Then the solvent for extraction (ethanol) was filled. For extraction temperature should maintain 500.

c. Extraction was carried out until discoloration of solvents. After completion of the extraction procedure the extract was filtered using Whattman filter paper and then concentrated at 45°C. The product was collected and shade dried for 10 day and extract was powdered Dried extracts were stored in well closed container at 20°C until further test were carried out. Percentage yield of latex: Percentage yield of extract was calculated by dividing the Weight of extract by the Weight of the leaf powder taken for extraction.

Preparation of Material

Vigna Radiata , Azadirachta Indica , Cicer Arietinum , Mangifera Indica were collected, shade dried at room temperature and Ground in a manual mill and sieved with 2 mm copper sieve to form uniform powder. 50 g of dried powdered drug was weighed and filled in the thimble.

Formulation of facial scrub

Preparation of active ingredients Weigh all ingredients as given in formulation table. Mix them uniformly using mortar and pastel.

Add prepared gel

The gel was added to the active ingredient mixture and mixed. The produced Formulation was then assessed utilizing several parameters. And stirred the produced mixture five batches i.e F1,F2,F3,F4,F5 Of herbal face scrub were formulated.

Sr.No	Ingredient % w/v	Category	Batches				
			F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1.	Mangifera Indica (g)	Active Ingredient	0.3	0.4	1	0.7	0.3
2.	Azadirachta Indica (g)	Active Ingredient	0.2	1	0.6	0.6	0.7
3.	Cicer Arietinum (g)	Scrubbing Agent	0.4	0.6	0.4	0.7	0.3
4.	Vigna Radiata (g)	Scrubbing Agent	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.3	0.8
5.	Sodium Lauryl Sulphate (g)	Surfactant	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
6.	Methyl Paraben (g)	Preservative	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
7.	Glycerine (g)	Humectant	3	3	3	3	3
8.	Rose Water	Flavouring Agent	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs
9.	Curcuma Longa (g)	Active Ingredient	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Identification and authentication of the plant

The specimen of Mangifera Indica , Azadirachta Indica , Curcuma Longa , Cicer Arietinum , Vigna Radiata, were collected in plastic bag form Dips college campus Pohetakali, pathri dist Parbhani, state Maharashtra, India during the month of may and then it was and then it was processed and of plan sheet as per procedure of botanical survey of India for identification and authenticated by Prof. Dr. K.S. Kadam, Asst professor in botany, department of Botany.K.K.M.Science

college Manwath dist Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.

Physiological Characterization

Organoleptic characteristics of the selected were assessed using natural sense like nose. Eyes mouth; physical appearance, odour, nature. Following result presented in Organoleptic Characteristic of Mangifera indica leaves extracted.

Organoleptic Characteristic of Mangifera indica leaves extract

Sr. No	Parameter	Observation of Extract	
		ET	ME
1	Physical Appearance	Sticky mass	Sticky paste
2	Colour	Greenish black	Greenish
3	Odour	Characteristic	Characteristic
4	Taste	Slightly bitter	Slightly bitter

Organoleptic Characteristic of Azadirachta indica leaves extract

Sr. No	Parameter	Observation of Extract	
		ET	ME
1	Physical Appearance	Sticky mass	Sticky paste
2	Colour	Greenish black	Greenish
3	Odour	Characteristic	Characteristic
4	Taste	Slightly bitter	Slightly bitter

Result of Phytochemical Characterisation

Sr. No	Class of Compounds	Test Performed	Results
I	Alkaloids	Mayer's test / Dragendroff's test	+
Ii	Amino acid	Ninhydrin test	-
Iii	Carbohydrate	Molisch's test	+
Iv	Fats & fixed oil	Glycerine test	-
V	Flavonoids	Alkaline reagent test	+
Vi	Glycosides	Borntrager test	+
Vii	Mucilage	Ruthenium red test	-
Viii	Protein	Biuret test	-
Ix	Saponins	Froth formation Test	+
X	Steroids	Salkowski test	-
Xi	Tannins	Ferric chloride test	+
Xii	Terpenoids	Liebermann-burchard Test	+
Xiii	Volatile oil	Sudan III test	-
Xiv	Heavy metals	Limit test	-
Xv	Starch	Iodine test	-

Phytochemical Analysis: Present= (+), Absent= (-)

SUMMARY

Plants have been used for health and medicinal purpose from several years. Now day's herbal

preparation are more popular because of their less side effect and disease curing properties Aim of present work was to formulate herbal face scrub having exfoliating properties . Formulation was

subject to various evaluation tests like, colour Greenish brown, small greenness included, pH- 5, spreadability good, nonirritant, having small gritty particles, easily washable, easily Extrudible, having good foaming ability and good stability. Formulated face scrub test for dermatologist activity have not produce any irritation. The face scrubs having the good activity when compared with standard face scrubs the face scrub were found to be stable under condition of room temperature of 40°C.

CONCLUSION

The prepared face scrub was found to be stable effective and safe.

REFERENCES

1. Charulata T. Nemade, Nayana Baste; Rmulation And Evaluation Of A Herbal Facial Scrub. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research Volume 3, Issue 3, 4367-4371.
2. Mounikal, Priya Kumari Sinha, Dr Kavitha P.N; Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Face Scrub Using Exfoliating Agents. International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR) E-ISSN: 2582-2160
3. Dr. Shweta P. Ghode, Vibhavari M. Chatur, Dr. Prashant D. Ghode, 3 Nikhil Shaha, Satyajeeet Prajapati and Atul Thorave; Formulation And Evaluation Of Facial Scrub Containing Sunflower Seeds And Other Natural Ingredients Pharmaceutical Research, Volume 8, Issue 9, 1772-1781.
4. Sejal Mahajan and Dr. Nandu Kayande; Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal scrub, international Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology (IJARSCT), Volume 3, Issue 2, April 2023
5. Mounika , Priya Kumari Sinha , Dr Kavitha P.N Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Face Scrub Using Exfoliating Agents International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research E-ISSN: 2582-2160
6. Shoeb Akhtar, Shivani Saini, Dr. S.M. Patil. Formulation And Evaluation Of Facial Herbal Scrub By Using Sesame Seeds © 2023 IJNRD | Volume 8, Issue 2023
7. Rutuja Prashant nangare, Trupti Ashok Thange. Formulation and Evaluation of herbal face scrub International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews, Vol 3, no 6, pp 3439-3448, 2022
8. Vidya keshavkakat, nishigandha nandkishor dhokale, rutujanjanaysanap ,shahinarafiquesayyed. A review on: herbal face scrub for skin exfoliation. 2022 ijcr | volume 10, issue 2022.
9. Pooja Dave, Gira Patel, Devanshi Patel, Binkal Patel, Dipti Patel, G S Chakraborty, Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Face Scrub containing Coffea arabica Linn, Myristica fragrans, and Lens culinaris as an Antioxidant and Antiseptic Activity 2022
10. Hirudkar, V. N., & Shivhare, V. (2022). A review on Ayurvedic cosmeceuticals and their mode of actions. Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics, 12(6), 204–206.
11. Kumar, S., Palbag, S., Maurya, S. K., & Kumar, D. (2013). Skin care in Ayurveda: A literary review. International Research Journal of Pharmacy, 4(3).
12. McMullen, R. L., & Dell'Acqua, G. (2023). History of natural ingredients in cosmetics. Cosmetics, 10, 71.
13. Jaybhaye Pawan Formulation & Evaluation Of Face Scrub © 2023 IJNRD | Volume 8, Issue 2023 | ISSN: 2456-4184
14. Harshal Prakash Salve, Shirsath P.R, Sumedh Mahendra Shoshte, Shreyas Waman, Vaishnavi Manoj Kangane Formulation And Evaluation Study
15. Prashant Ravsaheb Chaudhari, Dr. Hemant V. Kamble, Prof. Mayur M. Garje Formulation

And Evaluation Of Herbal Scrub 2024 IJCRT
| Volume 12, Issue 2024 | ISSN: 2320-2882

skin exfoliation. 2022 ijcr | volume10, issue
2022.

16. Ms.Reshma U. Jadhav, Ms Bhavana D. Tambe Face Scrub by Herbal Drugs international journal of novel research and development IJNRD ISSN 2456-4184
17. Vidya Keshav kakad, nishigandha nandkishor dhokale, rutuja sanjay sanap, shahina Rafique sayyed. A review on: herbal face scrub for

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